

EVALUATION OF INTERFACIAL DEBONDING AND FIBER PULL-OUT
STRESSES OF SiC FIBER-REINFORCED GLASSES

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ABSTRACT

Interfacial behavior of SiC fiber reinforced glass matrix composites was analyzed by a single fiber pull-out testing. The interfacial properties of this composite were calculated by using Hsueh's shear-lag analysis during the fiber pull-out tests in terms of interfacial shear strength, coefficient of friction and residual clamping stress. Experimental difference of load-time curves between materials can be explained by the analysis of shear stress distribution of fiber.

KEYWORDS: Composites; Glass matrix; Ceramic fiber; Pull-out test; Interfacial strength; Residual stress.

1. INTRODUCTION

Many ceramic matrix composites have been investigated to enhance fracture toughness of ceramics. Especially in continuous fiber reinforced ceramics remarkable increase of toughness has been reported (1, 2, 3). In such composites it is very important that the mechanism of stress shielding can enhance fracture toughness, due to crack bridging and sliding at interface between matrix and fiber. Consequently, interfacial shear stress or strength determines the increasing of fracture toughness with crack extension, which is called as R-curve behavior.

The purpose of this paper is to estimate the interfacial mechanical properties quantitatively by a single fiber pull-out testing. The SiC fiber reinforced glass composite was used as a model material where friction between matrix and fiber provides stress transfer. The interfacial shear strength of this composite was calculated by using Hsueh's shear-lag analysis (4). Also the debonding behavior at the interface was observed by the video microscope system with high magnification. The debonding process in this composite will be discussed in the consideration of the stress distribution of a fiber which is estimated by this model.

2. THEORY

2.1 Interfacial Parameters Analysis of interfacial shear stress in the single fiber pull-out test was carried out by Hsueh (4) by using the configuration of the single fiber pull-out test (see Figure 1) and the stress vs. displacement curve (see Figure 2). Here the frictional debonding process is assumed, that is, stress is always transferred by the friction at interface. The interfacial shear strength, τ_s , is used as a criterion for debonding, which can be represented as

$$\tau_s = -\sigma_d \left\{ \frac{(b^2/a^2-1)(E_m/E_f)\coth(\alpha t)+2/[\exp(\alpha t)-\exp(-\alpha t)]}{(2/a)[(1+\nu_m)\{1+(b^2/a^2-1)(E_m/E_f)\}\{b^2 \ln(b/a)-(b^2-a^2)/2\}]^{1/2}} \right\}, \quad (1)$$

where a is the radius of fiber, b is the radius of specimen, t is the embedded length of fiber, E_m and E_f are Young's modulus of matrix and fiber, V_m and V_f are volume fraction, ν_m and ν_f are Poisson's ratio and σ_d is the initial stress of partial debonding. Also the coefficient of friction, μ , and residual clamping stress, σ_c , can be obtained from the following equations,

$$\begin{aligned} & \left\{ \frac{E_m V_f}{E_f V_m} \left[1 - \frac{b^2}{a^2} \right] - 1 \right\} [\exp(m_1 t) - \exp(m_2 t)] \\ & + \frac{aD}{2\mu\nu_m} \left[1 - \frac{b^2}{a^2} \right] \{m_1 [1 - \exp(m_2 t)] - m_2 [1 - \exp(m_1 t)]\} \\ & = -\frac{a}{2\mu} \left[m_1 [1 - \exp(m_2 t)] - m_2 [1 - \exp(m_1 t)] + (m_1 - m_2) \left\{ \frac{E_m V_f}{E_f V_m} \left[1 - \frac{b^2}{a^2} \right] - 1 \right\} \right] \frac{\sigma_t}{\sigma_c}, \quad (2) \\ & \frac{(m_1 - m_2) \exp\{(m_1 + m_2)t\} \sigma_d}{\exp(m_1 t) - \exp(m_2 t)} \\ & = \frac{A_3 m_2 \exp(m_2 t) - m_1 \exp(m_1 t) + (m_1 - m_2) \exp\{(m_1 + m_2)t\}}{A_2 \exp(m_1 t) - \exp(m_2 t)} \\ & + \frac{2\mu}{a} \sigma_c + \sigma_d \left\{ \frac{m_1 \exp(m_1 t) - m_2 \exp(m_2 t)}{\exp(m_1 t) - \exp(m_2 t)} + \frac{2\mu E_m V_f}{aD E_f} \right\}, \quad (3) \end{aligned}$$

where

$$\begin{aligned} \alpha &= \frac{1}{a} \left[\frac{a^2 E_f + (b^2 - a^2) E_m}{E_f (1 + \nu_m) \{b^2 \ln(b/a) - (b^2 - a^2)/2\}} \right]^{1/2}, \quad D = \frac{b^2 + a^2}{b^2 - a^2} + \nu_m + \frac{E_m (1 - \nu_f)}{E_f}, \\ A_1 &= \frac{a(1 - b^2/a^2)D}{2\mu\nu_m(1 + \nu_m)\{b^2 \ln(b/a) - (b^2 - a^2)/2\}}, \quad A_2 = \frac{(1 - b^2/a^2)(E_m V_f/E_f \nu_m) - 1}{(1 + \nu_m)\{b^2 \ln(b/a) - (b^2 - a^2)/2\}}, \\ A_3 &= -\frac{\sigma_d^* + (\sigma_c/\nu_m)(1 - b^2/a^2)D}{(1 + \nu_m)\{b^2 \ln(b/a) - (b^2 - a^2)/2\}}, \\ m_1 &= \{-A_1 - (A_1^2 - 4A_2)^{1/2}\}/2, \quad m_2 = \{-A_1 + (A_1^2 - 4A_2)^{1/2}\}/2, \quad (4) \end{aligned}$$

σ_d^* is the stress of complete debonding and σ_t is the stress of fiber pull-out.

Denote σ_p as the radial stress of interface at the position of surface of matrix which is induced by applied stress, σ_h .

FIGURE 1. Configuration of the single fiber pull-out test.

FIGURE 2. Stress vs. displacement curve during the single fiber pull-out test.

$$\sigma_p = \frac{\frac{v_f}{E_f} \sigma_h}{\frac{(1-v_f)}{E_f} + \frac{b^2+a^2}{E_m} + v_m} \quad (5)$$

This partial debonding process can be valid for the frictional debonding condition, $\sigma_c + \sigma_p > 0$. The interfacial frictional stress at the surface, τ_i , can be represented as

$$\tau_i = \mu (\sigma_c + \sigma_p). \quad (6)$$

2.2 Frictionless Debonding If the length of fiber is long or the interfacial shear strength is strong relatively, the condition, $\sigma_c + \sigma_p \leq 0$, is satisfied, which is called as frictionless debonding. Here stress is not transferred effectively, and debonding would occur catastrophically. Two parameters, coefficient of friction and residual clamping stress can be not calculated without assumptions.

3. EXPERIMENTAL

3.1 Materials The composite, which was used in the experiment, consists of SiC fiber (TEXTRON, SCS-6) and Pyrex glass (Corning, #7740). The fibers with an average diameter of 150 μm were aligned in a layer at equal spacing and were covered with two glass sheets. The samples were hot-pressed at 1,023 K and a pressure of 10 MPa in both vacuum (type A) and Ar gas (type B).

FIGURE 3. Geometry of specimen.

FIGURE 4. Experimental system with video microscope.

3.2 Single Fiber Pull-out Test The specimens were cut from these sheets and polished. Figure 3 shows the geometry of specimen used in single fiber pull out testing. Notch was induced to crack matrix. A specimen was pulled out vertically by Instron type tensile machine and the load to fiber was measured. The observation from side view of specimen during pull-out test was employed by the video microscope system (Scholar, VMS-1000), which is shown in Figure 4.

4. RESULTS

4.1 Debonding Behavior The micrograph of observation from side view of specimen of type A composite is shown in Figure 5. Figure 5 (a), (b) and (c) correspond to the intact interface, partial debonded interface and complete debonded interface, respectively. It is clear that debonding at interface propagates gradually and finally fiber pull-out occurs from the observation of interface.

4.2 Load-time Curves An example of time-load curves of type A composite during pull-out test are shown in Figure 6. Load increased linearly and then dropped suddenly because of matrix cracking. Load increased again and compliance changed accompanying partial debonding at interface. Step-like debonding occurred before complete debonding, and then fiber pull-out started. Figure 7 shows the time-load curves of type B composite during pull-out test. In this material, partial debonding of interface was not observed.

4.3 Interfacial Parameters Parameters that describe the interfacial characteristics such as interfacial shear strength, coefficient of friction, residual clamping stress and interfacial frictional stress at the surface were calculated from equations (1), (2), (3), (5) and (6). The estimated values of these materials are listed in Table 1. In the type B composite, the coefficient of friction was calculated by using the same value of the residual clamping stress as the type A composite since the specimen of the type B composite showed the frictionless debonding behavior and the temperature of fabrication was the same as that of the type A. The result of interfacial frictional stress demonstrates that the present model for debonding can explain the experimental difference of the load-time curves of two materials.

FIGURE 5. Micrograph of specimen from side view, (a) intact interface, (b) partially debonded interface, (c) completely debonded interface.

FIGURE 6. An example of time-load curves of type A composite during pull-out test.

FIGURE 7. An example of time-load curves of type B composite during pull-out test.

TABLE 1. Interfacial mechanical parameters of the SiC fiber glass matrix composites.

Material	type A	type B
Fabricated conditions	at 1023K in vacuum	at 1023K in Argon
Interfacial shear strength, τ_s (MPa)	100.3	175.0
Coefficient of friction, μ	0.41	0.41
Residual clamping stress, σ_c (MPa)	34.1	34.1
Induced radial stress by initial debonding, σ_p (MPa)	-23.1	-40.1
Induced radial stress by complete debonding, σ_p (MPa)	-31.3	-
Debonding behavior	Frictional debonding	Frictionless debonding

5. CONCLUSIONS

The interfacial parameters of the SiC fiber reinforced glass matrix composite have been measured by the single fiber pull-out test. The debonding behavior at the interface was observed by the video microscope system with high magnification. By using modified shear-lag model interfacial mechanical parameters such as interfacial shear strength, frictional coefficient and residual clamping stress, were successfully obtained from experimental results of initial debonding stress, complete debonding stress and fiber pull-out stress in a single fiber pull-out test. It could be concluded that the present analysis demonstrates the experimental difference between frictional debonding and frictionless debonding.

6. REFERENCES

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